

Potentiometric and Biocidal Studies of Ternary Complexes of Some Transition Metals with 2-Carboxy,2'-Hydroxy Diphenylamine (DPHC) and Some Bidentate Ligands

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Synthesis and characterisation of a new ligand, 2-carboxy,2'-hydroxy diphenylamine has been described. The potentiometric studies on the binary and ternary complexes of the above ligand with some transition metal ions (Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+}) have been carried out. The dissociation constants of free ligand and the stability constants for 1 : 1, M-L and 1 : 1 : 1, M-L-L' [M = metal ions, L = 2-carboxy,2'-hydroxy diphenylamine (DPHC) and L' = nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA)] have been evaluated at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ in 2.5% ethanolic medium. The systems 1 : 1 : 1, M(II)-DPHC-HQ (HQ = 8-hydroxyquinoline) were also studied pH-metrically. The copper complex was isolated, characterised and tested for its fungicidal and bactericidal activities towards some selected species.

A survey of the literature revealed that binary and ternary chelates of *o*-aminophenol with a number of transition metal ions have been studied¹⁻². 2,2'-Dicarboxy diphenylamine has been synthesised and pH-metric studies on its complexation with some transition metal ions have been made by previous workers³.

In this paper, synthesis and characterisation (elemental and ir spectral analysis) of a new ligand, 2-carboxy,2'-hydroxy diphenylamine (DPHC) from *o*-aminophenol and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid have been described. The proton dissociation constants of DPHC have been calculated. The binary and ternary complex formation involving DPHC and other bidentate ligands such as NTA and HQ with some transition metal ions (Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+}) has been studied potentiometrically with a view to determine their formation constants. The insoluble ternary complex 1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ has been isolated, characterised and studied for its bioactive effects using different available strains of fungi and bacteria.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH or E. Merck grade. Solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardised by the usual methods⁴.

Stock solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline monohydrochloride (HQ.HCl) was obtained by dissolving known amount of oxine in 0.1 M HCl. The solution of desired concentration was obtained by subsequent dilution.

Solution of NTA, used in diprotonated form, was obtained on dissolving the weighed amount of the substance in equimolar amount of standard KOH.

DPHC solution was obtained by dissolving its weighed amount in 50% alcoholic solution.

Synthesis of 2-carboxy,2'-hydroxy diphenylamine : The alcoholic solution of 2.728 g (0.025 mol) *o*-aminophenol was treated with potassium salt of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid prepared by dissolving 3.94 g (0.025 mol) acid in a saturated solution of 1.725 g (0.012 mol) K_2CO_3 . The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 5 h. Activated charcoal was then added and refluxed for another 0.5 h and the mixture was filtered. On acidifying the filtrate with dilute HCl a dark coloured substance was obtained which on recrystallization from alcohol yielded a crystalline product, m.p. 140° . (Found : C, 68.03 ; H, 4.77 ; N, 6.05. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_3$; C, 68.12 ; H, 4.80 ; N, 6.11%).

Potentiometric studies : The pH titration of the systems were conducted using Philips digital pH-meter PP 9045.

For the systems M(II)-DPHC-NTA the pH-metric titrations were conducted with 0.1 M KOH, at varying ionic concentrations (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 M KNO_3), keeping the total volume at 50 ml and temp. $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Calculations : The proton dissociation constants ($pK_1 = 2.75 \pm 0.13$ and $pK_2 = 9.32 \pm 0.20$) of DPHC were calculated by the method of Chaberele and

TABLE 1

System	log K_{ME}	ΔF° kcal mol ⁻¹	log $K_{MLL'}$			log K_o for 1 : 1 : 1 species	ΔF° at log K_o kcal mol ⁻¹
			0.1	0.2	0.3		
1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC	11.73±0.12	-15.97	18.72±0.19	18.65±0.12	18.58±0.11	18.81	-25.63
1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-NTA	11.22±0.20	-15.29	18.22±0.06	18.09±0.10	17.96±0.07	18.34	-24.99
1 : 1, Ni(II)-DPHC	10.61±0.20	-14.46	17.61±0.19	17.32±0.16	17.10±0.19	17.82	-24.28
1 : 1 : 1, Ni(II)-DPHC-NTA	10.52±0.18	-14.33	17.10±0.18	17.04±0.20	16.98±0.19	17.14	-23.36
1 : 1, Zn(II)-DPHC							
1 : 1 : 1, Zn(II)-DPHC-NTA							
1 : 1, Cd(II)-DPHC							
1 : 1 : 1, Cd(II)-DPHC-NTA							

M(II)=Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II); L = DPHC; L' = NTA

TABLE 2

DPHC		HQ		Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ	
Characteri- stic frequ- encies cm ⁻¹	Assignments	Charac- teristic frequen- cies cm ⁻¹	Assignments	Charac- teristic frequen- cies* cm ⁻¹	Assignments
2860-2760 b	-OH bonds	3270 s	-OH stretching	3375 b	splitting of NH
2550 w	-COOH group	3100 s	C-H bond	1680 s	coordinated H ₂ O molecules
1640 s	-C=O	1660 m	C=C	1385 s	M-OH bond
1540 s	C=C	1610 s	-C=N stretching	1340 s	C-N vibrations
1390 m	-OH deformation in COOH group	1585 s	aromatic character	1300 w	NH- phenyl group
1340 s	phenolic OH			1255 w	C=O
900 w	-C-O stretching			1130 m	M-OH bond
765 m	ortho substituted aromatic ring			580 s	M-N bond
740 m	-C-N stretching			445 m	M-O bond

* b = broad, s = sharp, m = medium, w = weak

Martell⁵ and the stability constants for binary and ternary complexes by the respective methods of Thompson and Loraas⁶ and Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁷. The values of the formation constants are consolidated in Table 1.

In order to substantiate the results of potentiometric studies, 1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ was isolated and characterised by ir spectra (Table 2). (Found: C, 58.22; H, 3.72; N, 6.17; Cu, 13.98. Calcd. for CuC₂₂H₁₂O₄N₂·H₂O; C, 58.34; H, 3.75; N, 6.18; Cu, 14.03%.)

IR studies of DPHC and its Cu(II)-ternary complex: IR spectra studies of DPHC, and its ternary complex 1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ, and HQ are given in Table 2.

On the basis of assignments made for the constituent groups present in the ligand the following tentative structure may be proposed for the compound 2-carboxy, 2'-hydroxy diphenylamine (DPHC).

Biocidal studies of 1:1:1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ complex: The isolated insoluble complex 1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ, has been tested for its antifungal and antibacterial activities towards some of the fungi *Drechshra tetramera*, *Penicillium nigricans*, and

Candida albicans and bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. A comparison of the activity of the above ternary species has been made with the activities of the ligands involved and that of binary 1 : 1, Cu(II)-HQ complex. The results are recorded in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 3—MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) OBSERVED AGAINST INDICATED FUNGI

Substance	<i>D. tetramera</i>	<i>A. nigricans</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	50.0	50.0	—
DPHC	3.1	6.1	12.5
HQ	12.5	25.0	—
1 : 1, Cu(II)-HQ	12.5	25.0	25.0
1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ	3.1	3.1	6.2

TABLE 4—MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) OBSERVED AGAINST INDICATED FUNGI

Substance	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	50.0	50.0	50.0
DPHC	6.2	12.2	25.0
HQ	12.5	25.0	—
1 : 1, Cu(II)-HQ	12.5	25.0	50.0
1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ	3.1	6.2	3.1

Results and Discussion

For the following discussion, the systems (1 : 1 : 1, M(II)-DPHC-NTA/HQ H⁺) involving

Cu^{2+} has been chosen as representative and those of the Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} being identical are omitted for the sake of brevity.

Curve b in Figs. 1 and 3 represents the pH-metric titration of free ligand, DPHC. Single sharp inflection at $m=1$ may be attributed to the titration of $-\text{COOH}$ proton in DPHC.

Fig. 1. System 1 : 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-DPHC-NTA.
 b DPHC
 c NTA
 d 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-DPHC
 e 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-NTA
 f 1 : 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-DPHC-NTA
 → Indicates stages of disproportionation
 T & T' Theoretical composite curve

Curve c in Figs. 1 and 3 represents the titration of mono-potassium salt of NTA and HQH^+ , respectively. A single sharp inflection at $m=1$ may be ascribed to the titration of $-\text{COOH}$ proton in case of potassium salt of NTA and hydrochloride proton in the case of HQH^+ .

Curve d in Figs. 1 and 3 depicts the titration of 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC. Lowering in pH as compared to that of free DPHC and an inflection at $m=2$, may be correlated to the formation of 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC species during which the protons of COOH and phenolic groups of DPHC are made labile. The 1 : 1 binary species appears to undergo disproportionation giving a more stable 1 : 2, Cu(II)-DPHC complex and metal hydroxide, which is evidenced by another inflection at $m=3$.

Fig. 2. ●—● 1 : 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-DPHC-NTA
 ○—○ 1 : 1 : 1 ; Ni(II)-DPHC-NTA
 ▲—▲ 1 : 1 : 1 ; Zn(II)-DPHC-NTA
 △—△ 1 : 1 : 1 ; Cd(II)-DPHC-NTA

Fig. 3. System 1 : 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ.
 b DPHC
 c HQ
 d 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-DPHC
 e 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-HQ
 f 1 : 1 : 1 ; Cu(II)-DPHC-HQ
 → Appearance of ppt.

Curve e in respective Figs. 1 and 3 depicts the titrations of 1 : 1, Cu(II)-NTA and 1 : 1, Cu(II)-HQH⁺. The lowering in pH and inflection at m=2 may be attributed to the simultaneous involvement of the two -COOH groups of mono potassium salt of NTA and one phenolic and hydrochloride protons of HQ.H⁺, in the respective formation of 1 : 1, Cu(II)-NTA and 1 : 1, Cu(II)-HQ complexes. In the latter case the insoluble binary species formed from the very beginning appears to undergo disproportionation forming 1 : 2 species and metal hydroxide as is evidenced by an additional inflection at m=3 in curve e Fig. 3.

Curve f in Fig. 1 depicting the titration of 1 : 1 : 1, M(II)-DPHC-NTA system indicates an extensive lowering in pH compared to that observed in the binary systems and a well defined inflection at m=4, which is attributed to the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-NTA species and is further substantiated by the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve⁸ [respectively drawn by adding the horizontal distances of the curve 1 : 1, Cu(II)-NTA to DPHC and 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC to NTA]. The non-formation of heterogeneous phase throughout the titration and development of characteristic brown colour in solution near the inflection are the additional evidences for the formation of a soluble stable ternary species.

The systems involving other metals being identical, the formation of the ternary species may be depicted by general expression given below

(M²⁺ = Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺, A.2H⁺ = DPHC ;
B.2H⁺ = monopotassium salt of NTA)

The values of formation constants of the ternary species determined at varying ionic concentrations are recorded in Table 1.

From these, the thermodynamic stability constants of the ternary species have been found by extrapolation of the curves plotted for log K vs ionic strength (Table 1 and Fig. 2).

The stabilities of the complexes follow the Irving William's natural order⁹,

On the basis of potentiometric studies made, the following tentative structure (A) may be suggested for the 1 : 1 : 1, M(II)-DPHC-NTA species

Curve f in Fig. 3 for 1 : 1 : 1, Cu(II)-DPHC-HQH⁺ exhibits an extensive lowering in pH in comparison to that observed in the case of binary system and a well defined inflection at m=4, indicating the formation of a sparingly soluble ternary species during which COOH and phenolic groups of the ligands and hydrochloride proton of HQH⁺ get

involved. The ternary complex is granular and darker in intensity compared to the green precipitate formed in the system 1 : 1, Cu(II)-HQH⁺.

(A)

The comparison of frequencies observed in the ir spectra of free ligands and the ternary complex (Table 2) revealed the following :

The -OH stretching frequency at ~ 3270 cm⁻¹ observed in free HQH⁺, and OH(COOH) frequency at ~2550 and 900 cm⁻¹ and phenolic -OH frequency at ~1340 cm⁻¹ in free DPHC are altogether absent in the spectra of the complex indicating the involvement of phenolic group of HQ, and -COOH and -OH groups of DPHC in complex formation. The absorption frequencies at ~580 and ~445 cm⁻¹ are attributed respectively to M-N and M-O bonds in the complex. The presence of coordinated water molecule in the complex is revealed by a band occurring at ~1680 cm⁻¹.

On the basis of analytical and ir data the following tentative structure (B) may be proposed for the ternary complex.

(B)

Biocidal studies :

The biocidal activity of the mixed ligand chelate is found to be considerably higher as compared to that of the free metal ion, ligands and binary complexes. The increased activity of the mixed ligand complex may, probably, be attributed either to the combined bioactive effects of the metal and both the ligands present in the complex or to the increased liposoluble nature of the complex. Besides, increased diffusion of the metal complex through the cell-membrane of fungi and bacteria

may also play a significant role in increasing the fungicidal and bactericidal activity of the metal complex. The growth inhibition of the tested fungi and bacteria may be due to the exchange of trace metals of the metalloenzymes (present in the cell fluids and responsible for the growth) with the metal of the complex under test. This may bring about a change in the nature of the enzyme activity.

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